

A 6.78MHz Semi-Synchronous Rectifier for Deep Biomedical Implant Applications

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Abstract—Inductive powering is a popular choice for powering of wireless implants, but at high implant depth the link efficiency and hence available power drop dramatically. To compensate for this the link frequency may be increased, leading to increased power consumption of the active rectifier. This work proposes a semi-synchronous rectifier which consumes from 9.1μW down to 1.6μW dynamic power, allowing consumption to scale with a number of resonant cycles used to store energy in the receiver resonant element, increasing efficiency and output power. The proposed circuit is implemented in TSMC 180nm CMOS and measured, allowing operation from 20mW transmitted power at up to 135mm distance in phantom, using a 50mm and 7.5mm radius TX and RX coil respectively.

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a growing interest in advanced electronic implants for chronic monitoring and therapies like neuromodulation or targeted drug delivery. Powering long-term deep implants remains challenging because batteries complicate implantation, increase form factor and have limited lifetime. Alternatives like energy harvesters and fuel cells are still too unreliable or have too limited lifespan. Ultrasound or far-field electromagnetic powering have to deal with significant reflections at the skin-air interface and due to the non-homogeneity of the human body. By contrast, since the relative magnetic permeability of the body is close to 1, magnetic field lines do not get deflected by it. This is an important advantage of inductive powering, which is proven safe, is very well understood, and remains by far the most popular choice for wireless powering of implants. However, applying inductive powering for deep tissue implants remains very challenging.

As shown in Fig. 1 the end-to-end efficiency of the WPT system is the product of the link, storage and converter efficiencies. While inductive powering is efficient over short distances, the coupling factor k between the radiating coil L_{TX} and the implanted coil L_{RX} decreases rapidly with the depth. Since the transmitted power is limited by Specific Absorption Rate limits, deep tissue implants will typically receive very low available power levels (P_{av} , the maximum power which can be extracted from the LC-Tank using a perfectly matched load). Since both quality factors Q_{TX} and Q_{RX} are increasing with the operating frequency, η_{link} can be improved by operating at high frequencies up to several

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Fig. 1: Overview of inductive power transfer using resonant LC-Tanks between a TX and RX coil, with on the RX-side a half-wave rectifier (a). The different control mechanisms considered in this paper are shown (b, c, d), together with examples of their operating waveforms.

MHz. While this does not change the design requirements of the boost converter in the WPT chain, which may be implemented similar to energy harvesting systems such as [1], the increased frequency imposes significant and conflicting design challenges on the rectifier, which should be able to operate from low P_{av} with extremely low quiescent power consumption while operating at such high frequencies.

II. CONVENTIONAL ARCHITECTURES

Current-Mode (CM) rectifiers [2] may be used when low P_{av} is expected, because of their capability to boost the output voltage by opening the LC resonant tank at a suitable

Fig. 2: Architecture overview of the semi-synchronous rectifier as proposed in this paper. Z_L here represents a load impedance, which in a full WPT system will be a boost converter to upconvert the low V_{out} to the supply voltage of the ASIC.

Fig. 3: Edge Detector Cell schematics and its typical operating waveforms. Output OUT_n is used to control the switch MN and the calibration of the Falling Edge Detector, whereas OUT_p is used for the calibration of the Rising Edge Detector.

moment. The basic idea behind CM is to open the LC parallel resonant tank when the inductor current is maximum, allowing the coil to behave as an ideal current source to charge the output. However, the switch used to open the LC tank in CM such as in [2] must have a low on-resistance to avoid Q-factor reduction. Unfortunately, a low on-resistance requires large devices which inevitably leads to large dynamic losses at high operating frequencies. Therefore, this work instead employs Voltage-Mode (VM) operation [3], [4]. But, contrary to standard VM, we propose to first accumulate energy in the receiver LC tank during a few cycles of the carrier frequency (Fig. 1b). Only after a certain number of cycles (N_{opt}) of energy accumulation will the switch MN be closed to dump the charge into V_{out} , reducing switching losses and increasing the amplitude of the LC-Tank voltage v_{LC} . N_{opt} is numerically optimized to balance dynamic losses versus the energy extracted per charging cycle.

While this approach reduces dynamic switching losses from MN , the comparator (CMP0) power consumption is now dominant. To tackle this problem, this work proposes to disable CMP0 while the tank is resonating and only turn it on when N_{opt} cycles have passed. While this sounds trivial, it would

Fig. 4: Schematic diagram of the self-calibration block applied to the Delay and Edge Detector blocks. The reference waveforms are generated by a synchronous rectifier control, which is also used as a comparison reference during the measurements.

Fig. 5: Schematic diagram (a) and example of the operating waveforms (b) of the analog delay cell. As the size of the head of the current mirror is programmable, I_B can be kept constant and very small, hence the power consumption is dominated by the charging of C_d . The RESET signal is generated from a falling edge of TRIG.

need a clock synchronized to v_{LC} which in itself requires an always-on comparator. Instead, this work introduces a calibrated delay block to turn on/off the comparator (Fig. 1). To ensure correct functionality, the comparator must react very fast when turned on, which is not possible with standard comparator design without large power consumption. To tackle this, we introduce a fully dynamic Edge Detector Cell (EDC) which is able to perform this function without any static power consumption. This results in a semi-synchronous rectifier where the EDC is turned on during charge transfer to the load and thus the operations are periodically resynchronized to the magnetic field (Fig. 1d).

III. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 2 shows the block diagram of the proposed IC with the Delay Cell and EDC controlling the gate of the switch MN . As further discussed below, both the Delay Cell and EDC suffer from PVT variations. To mitigate this issue, a Self-Calibration block is introduced to periodically recalibrate these blocks. Since temperature in the human body is fairly constant, recalibration is only needed once every few hours of continuous operation, as confirmed by simulations and measurements and hence has negligible impact on the efficiency of the rectifier.

The schematic of the EDC and its typical waveforms are shown in Fig. 3. The core of the circuit consists of 6 transistors

Fig. 6: Example transient waveform (a) and measurement results (b) of the synchronous and semi-synchronous rectifier control mechanisms applied under the same conditions on an LC-Tank circuit on a PCB of which the P_{av} can be controlled.

MP1-MP4 and MN1-MN2. Around the rising zero crossing of the coil voltage v_{LC} , ED_TRIG, provided by the Delay Cell must fall. Due to the propagation delay of INV1 both MP1 and MP2 will be on for a short time, pulling V_A up to V_{DD} . Then, the gate of MN1, DC-biased via resistance R to V_{BR} , continues to rise because of its AC coupling to v_{LC} via capacitance C , until the threshold voltage of MN1 is reached and V_A gets rapidly discharged to ground. The Falling Edge Detector works in a similar way, but with the gate of MN2 DC biased to V_{BF} and the AC signal v_{LC} connected to its source, in order to have a gain opposite in sign to the Rising Edge Detector. The bias voltages V_{BR} and V_{BF} are generated by injecting a 10nA current into a programmable diode array, designed to guarantee monotonicity and controlled by the self-calibration.

PVT variations will affect the EDC rising and falling thresholds. Similarly, the Delay Cell, implemented by means of a programmable current integrated by a capacitor as shown in Fig. 5, is also PVT sensitive. The Self-Calibration block shown in Fig. 3 will calibrate in sequence both the Delay Cell and the EDC. During self-calibration, the converter is operated in a synchronous manner as explained in Fig. 3 with comparator CMP0 and CMP1 extracting synchronous clocks CLK0 and CLK1 respectively. At the same time the Delay Cell and EDC are active, but their outputs are not used for rectification. A SAR calibration algorithm is executed to find the Delay Cell current which matches the rising edge of

Fig. 7: Measurement results of the synchronous and semi-synchronous rectifier control circuits applied to a wireless-power transfer setup with TX coil $4.64\mu\text{H}$, $\varnothing 100\text{mm}$ and RX coil $2.31\mu\text{H}$, $\varnothing 15\text{mm}$ arranged at the specified distance in the saline tank of Fig. 8.

CAL_REF (generated from CLK1) with the falling edge of DEL_TRIG, the output of the Delay Cell. Next, the rising and falling thresholds of the EDC are calibrated by adjusting V_{BR} and V_{BF} using a similar mechanism, but this time comparing the rising and falling edges of VGN_SYNC (generated from CLK0) with the outputs of the EDC (OUTn and OUTp). The calibration will ensure that, in semi-synchronous operations, the signal VGN_SEMI will match VGN_SYNC. As the bias voltages V_{BR} and V_{BF} are generated by means of a very low bias current, their respective settling times are relatively long. Hence to ensure that V_{BR} or V_{BF} has settled before evaluating the effect of its change, the MSB of a 13-bit counter CNT<12> is used during calibration to provide the timing of the SAR algorithm.

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

The proposed IC has been fabricated in TSMC 180nm CMOS. The die photo is shown in Fig. 9 and its active area is 0.4mm^2 . The chip has been characterized at 6.78MHz with an air-coil inductor of $1.5\mu\text{H}$, $Q = 16$, for P_{av} ranging from 5 to $50\mu\text{W}$. In both the synchronous and semi-synchronous rectifier modes the chip is configured to charge an output load to a constant voltage equal to 20% of the unloaded receiver LC-tank amplitude. Fig. 6a shows a comparison of the measured coil voltage v_{LC} waveforms both in the conventional synchronous and the proposed semi-synchronous modes. These measurements confirm that, thanks to the self-calibration, the semi-synchronous rectifier achieves the same control timing as the more conventional synchronous rectifier. However, it does so at a 5.8x lower power, thanks to the fully dynamic EDC. Fig. 6b shows the measured end-to-end rectification efficiency $\eta_{store} \cdot \eta_{conv}$ for both modes of operation with the semi-synchronous mode achieving signif-

TABLE I: State of the Art Comparison

	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]	This Work
Process [nm]	180	65	180 SOI	180	180	180	180	180
Operating Frequency [MHz]	0.05	13.56	144	13.56	13.56	13.56	13.56	6.78
Active Area [mm ²]	0.544	0.75	0.078	0.21	0.75	0.9	2.5	0.4
MRI Compatible	NO ¹	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Minimum P_{av} [μ W]	0.6 ²	3000 ³	5000 ³	2000 ³	56.2 ⁴	4000	600 ³	15
RX Coil Size	2.6x3.5x11.7mm ³	N.A.	8.64mm ² on-chip	7x7mm ²	10x10mm ²	29.3mm ϕ	10mm ϕ	15mm ϕ
TX Coil Size	N.A.	N.A.	25x25mm ²	N.A.	46x46mm ²	34.5mm ϕ	30mm ϕ	100mm ϕ
TX Power [mW]	20	N.A.	7.87	N.A.	200	> 60 ⁴	N.A.	20
Maximum Operating Distance in Phantom [mm]	55 Air + 30 Phantom	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	40	N.A.	N.A.	10 Air + 135 Phantom
Type of Phantom	Bovine Tissue	N.A.	Porcine Tissue	N.A.	Saline	Bovine Tissue and Saline	N.A.	Saline

¹Uses a Coilcraft 4513TC Receiver coil with magnetic core

²As understood from the paper, this is P_{in} , not P_{av} , with $P_{av} \geq P_{in}$

³Extrapolation from data in the paper

⁴Minimum based on data in the paper

Fig. 8: Picture of the measurement setup of the in-phantom measurements, with the depth of the RX coil in saline set at 85mm and the semi-synchronous rectifier operating at $N_{opt}=2$.

icantly higher efficiencies for low P_{av} . The minimum P_{av} at which power can be delivered to the load, found at $\eta = 0$, is $>50\mu$ W in synchronous mode, which reduces to 15μ W in semi-synchronous mode: a 3.3x improvement. This large difference is due to the fact that the output power generated in the two modes is very similar, but the power dissipated by the control circuits in semi-synchronous operations is much lower. To validate the performance in wireless power transfer, measurements in air using a 4.64μ H transmit coil transmitting 20mW of power and a 2.31μ H receive coil were performed, of which the results are shown in Fig. 7. Furthermore, this same setup was tested using the phantom shown in Fig. 8 (3.7g/L of KCl in DI water), showing a maximum operating distance of 135mm in saline delivering 460nW to a 80mV load. This is the highest distance shown for inductive powering in-body, as indicated in Table I.

V. CONCLUSION

A comparison with the state of the art is shown in Table I. Only [2] can operate from a lower minimum P_{av} , but operates at 50kHz and hence needs a coil with a magnetic core to increase its Q-factor, at the expense of MRI compatibility. Compared to other prior art using air coils, and hence operating at higher frequencies to increase Q factor, the proposed IC has by far the smallest minimum P_{av} requirement, 3x better than [6]. Thanks to the novel semi-synchronous VM rectifier

Fig. 9: Picture of the die of the semi-synchronous rectifier chip manufactured in TSMC 180nm process. The active area of the described circuits is indicated.

with self-calibrated Delay Cell and Edge Detector cell, the proposed IC is able to wirelessly power deep tissue implants over unseen distances of up to 13.5cm in-body. This presents a significant leap forward in the field of inductive wireless powering, previously limited to short distances, unlocking new possibilities for deep-tissue implants.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Liu, Y. Xing, W. Huang, X. Liao, and Y. Li, "A 10 mV-500 mV Input Range, 91.4% Peak Efficiency Adaptive Multi-Mode Boost Converter for Thermoelectric Energy Harvesting," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 609–619, 2022.
- [2] M. Choi, T. Jang, J. Jeong, S. Jeong, D. Blaauw, and D. Sylvester, "A current-mode wireless power receiver with optimal resonant cycle tracking for implantable systems," in *Digest of Technical Papers - IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference*, vol. 59, 2016, pp. 372–373.
- [3] C. Huang, T. Kawajiri, and H. Ishikuro, "A Near-Optimum 13.56 MHz CMOS Active Rectifier with Circuit-Delay Real-Time Calibrations for High-Current Biomedical Implants," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 51, no. 8, pp. 1797–1809, 2016.
- [4] C. Kim, S. Ha, J. Park, A. Akinin, P. P. Mercier, and G. Cauwenberghs, "A 144-MHz Fully Integrated Resonant Regulating Rectifier with Hybrid Pulse Modulation for mm-Sized Implants," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 52, no. 11, pp. 3043–3055, 2017.
- [5] S. U. Shin, M. Choi, S. T. Koh, Y. Yang, S. Jung, Y. H. Sohn, S. H. Park, Y. Ju, Y. Jo, Y. Huh, S. Choi, S. J. Kim, and G. H. Cho, "A 13.56MHz time-interleaved resonant-voltage-mode wireless-power receiver with isolated resonator and quasi-resonant boost converter for implantable systems," *Digest of Technical Papers - IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference*, vol. 61, pp. 154–156, 2018.
- [6] H. Lee, S. Jung, Y. Huh, and S. J. Kim, "Wireless Power Receiver with Wide Dynamic Range for Biomedical Implants," *2019 IEEE Wireless Power Transfer Conference, WPTC 2019*, pp. 241–244, 2019.
- [7] Y. Engur, H. A. Yigit, and H. Kulah, "13.56 MHz Triple Mode Rectifier Circuit with Extended Coupling Range for Wirelessly Powered Implantable Medical Devices," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Circuits and Systems*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 68–79, 2021.
- [8] M. Kim, H. S. Lee, J. Ahn, and H. M. Lee, "A 13.56-MHz Wireless Power and Data Transfer System With Current-Modulated Energy-Reuse Back Telemetry and Energy-Adaptive Voltage Regulation," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 400–410, 2023.